

PREDICTION OF CRACK TORTUOSITY IN FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE MICROSTRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced laminates are an important structural material in the aerospace industry. With the advent of multifunctional materials and nanocomposites, the ability to engineer materials over decades of length scales is now possible and thus requires an understanding of the relationship between small scale structure and larger scale response. In this contribution, we focus on the fracture surface at the scale of the microstructure. The dependence of the tortuosity of the fracture surface through microstructures of various sizes and volume fractions is explored by determining a cleaving crack path requiring minimal fracture energy for each microstructure. A mathematical graph theory approach is used to calculate the minimal energy crack path.

1 INTRODUCTION

Qualification of material systems and certification of structures for use in aerospace or other applications are rigorous processes used to ensure safety of operation. These processes currently involve a great deal of empirical testing to populate property and performance databases which are used to generate design allowables. The amount of testing required is typically time consuming and can be very expensive and thus restricts the utilization of new material and design solutions. Rather, previously qualified materials are used to minimize the cost and development time. In order to move past this paradigm, a multiscale simulation approach to offset a portion of the empirical testing is attractive. The focus of this contribution is modelling damage at the scale of the microstructure with the intent of predicting properties for the lamina scale.

There are a few main methods by which mechanical damage at the microstructure scale of a composite is typically represented. Particulate, non-continuum approaches such as peridynamics [1] are being employed increasingly often due in part to the imbedded natural framework for fracture simulations. The continuum damage mechanics approach [2, 3] operates under the assumption that the effect of damage at finer length scales is a degradation of the local stiffness at the coarser scale. This approach is particularly attractive in a composite microstructure in which the stress field is far from uniform due to the reinforcements, voids, residual cure stress, etc. However, as seen in [4], property degradation on the ply level leads to nonphysical results for local stresses in the damage area and difficulties of damage mode interaction modelling. To address this issue, the discrete damage modelling (DDM) was proposed based on extended finite element method (XFEM) ideas [5] to model discrete cracks of arbitrary orientations independent of the mesh.

Multiscale analysis within the DDM framework can be accomplished in both fully coupled and simply coupled scale analysis (SCSA) settings with the simply coupled methods being especially attractive for practical applications. SCSA is an extension of the work [6] where stiffness homogenization and micro level stress bounds estimates were established for pre-stressed composites including regions with non-periodic microstructure. The proposed extension requires computation of

homogenized strength and fracture toughness properties. A direct simulation of failure progression on the micro level is generally required to accomplish this objective. One difficulty with this methodology is the need to determine a crack extension direction. Minimal energy fracture surface methods were applied in [7] to predict material properties from molecular simulations. In [8], the minimal energy crack path via A* (MECA*) method was defined and used in concert with the mesh independent crack modelling of [9] to define mesh independent cracks for the prediction of ply level strength and stiffness properties. In the present work, we utilize this simple approach to elucidate the dependence of the crack path tortuosity on microstructure parameters such as fiber volume fraction and matrix/interface fracture toughness.

2 METHODOLOGY

This section discusses the formulation used to compute the tortuosity of cracks through composite microstructures. It begins with a description of the MECA* method and concludes with the calculation of path tortuosity. We consider a 3D fiber-reinforced microstructure having a constant cross section (see Figure 1). We assume a unit out-of-plane (fiber direction) thickness, thus we can reduce our discussion of the fracture surface to the 2D length of the crack.

Figure 1: 2D slice of a fiber reinforced composite defining the tortuosity and modified tortuosity

2.2 Minimal Energy Fracture Surface

The discussion here follows the presentation in [8]. Consider the 2D slice of the composite architecture pictured in Figure 1. The gray areas are regions occupied by the fiber phase and the white areas are regions occupied by the matrix phase. Under normal tensile loading in the horizontal direction, a crack initiates and will propagate through the microstructure in the vertical direction. The goal is to determine a fracture surface (crack path) through the microstructure requiring the minimal amount of energy. The theory does not guarantee a single minimal energy path, so the case of multiple minima must, in general, be considered.

The method proceeds in three steps, discretization, graph creation, and path search. For the cases presented herein, the fibers are very unlikely to fracture. Thus, we restrict our discussion to the case consisting of matrix and interfacial failure only. If a discretization of the fiber boundaries is taken such that fibers are represented as polygonal objects, then the shortest path with obstacles problem is readily solved by constructing a visibility graph [10] and then using a shortest path algorithm such as the A* algorithm [11] or Dijkstra's algorithm [12].

We are not interested in the shortest length path, but the minimal energy path. The minimal energy path may not be the shortest length path due to the varying fracture toughnesses of the matrix and

interfaces. In the case when the matrix fracture toughness is equal to the interfacial fracture toughness, then the minimal energy path is identical to the shortest path with obstacles problem. The first step in the process, discretization, can be performed in any manner as long as it is clear which nodes belong to the matrix, interface, and fiber phases. The nodes will become the vertices in the graph, so the accuracy of the crack path and energy is proportional to the mesh density.

The next step is to create an undirected, weighted graph from the discretized model. We assume the total crack is piecewise linear between the vertices of the graph. Thus, we must use a criteria to determine which vertex pairs are allowed to have a crack (edge) connecting them. After all edges have been determined, we define the weight of the edge to be the fracture toughness multiplied by the distance between the vertices (since the model has out-of-plane dimension equal to 1). The fracture toughness for crack segments between vertices of the same material phase uses the appropriate material property. For a matrix-interface fracture or fiber-interface fracture, the non-interfacial fracture property is used (matrix or fiber, respectively).

We consider an edge to exist between two vertices if the distance between the vertices is less than a cut-off radius and either both points are in the same material phase or one vertex is an interface point (see Figure 2). Thus, a crack is not allowed to propagate directly from the matrix phase into the fiber phase without passing through an interface vertex. An additional criteria on edge determination is the visibility criteria. In complex microstructures (woven architectures, etc.) it may be possible to meet the above cut-off radius but pass through a different material phase. The visibility requirement solves this problem (see Figure 3).

To determine the minimal energy path, we need simply supply a set of initiation and termination points along with the weighted graph to the A* search algorithm and pick them minimum crack energy value.

Figure 2: Edge determination for the graph

Figure 3: Visibility restriction on edges of the graph

2.2 Tortuosity

The tortuosity of a curve in space does not have a single, accepted definition. For the purpose of this study, we use a simple yet common definition which is based strictly on the length of the fracture surface relative to the minimum length required to break the microstructure into two pieces. We assume that our fracture surfaces are rectifiable, and define the tortuosity τ of a curve as the arc-chord ratio, namely the ratio of the length of the fracture surface L to the distance between the endpoints of the fracture surface C (see Figure 1). Thus,

$$\tau = \frac{L}{C} \quad (1)$$

We are not simply interested in the tortuosity of the crack. We consider a so-called modified tortuosity τ^* , which is the ratio between the length of the crack L and the length of the straight line cleaving crack S_2 . This value gives the ratio of the total extension of the crack from the minimum cleaving crack length and is given by

$$\tau^* = \frac{L}{S_2} = \tau \left(\frac{C}{S_2} \right) \quad (2)$$

3 RESULTS

Eighty distinct microstructures having ten fibers each and 40%, 50%, 60%, and 70% fiber volume fraction were created (twenty, 10-fiber microstructures for each fiber volume fraction). The MECA* method was used to determine the minimal energy fracture surface through each microstructure. The microstructures were cubic and the fibers were cylindrical and of identical radius, thus the dimensions of each microstructure were completely determined by the number of fibers and the desired fiber volume fraction. Fibers were allowed to overlap the external boundary of the cell and, in that case, the fiber was repeated in a periodic fashion on the opposite boundaries. We did not allow fibers to fracture by assigning them a relatively large fracture toughness property (fracture surfaces were verified after the MECA* runs to ensure no fiber fractures occurred). The fracture energy properties for the matrix and interface were one of two selections: 1) the interface toughness equaled the matrix toughness, or

2) the interface toughness was 80% of the matrix toughness. In case 1), the minimal energy path is identical to the minimal length path and in case 2), the minimal energy path is typically longer than the minimal length path.

For each set of twenty microstructures having equal total fiber volume fraction and fracture properties, the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the modified tortuosity was computed. The results are plotted in Figure 4. As expected, the modified tortuosity of the microstructures with equal matrix and interface fracture toughness increases as the fiber volume fraction increases (red data in Figure 4). This relationship is expected because, in this case, the minimal energy crack path is the minimal length crack path. The crack path is more likely to encounter more fibers (obstacles) at higher volume fractions, thus the path will be longer (more tortuous). In the case of reduced interface fracture toughness (blue data in Figure 4), the modified tortuosity remains approximately constant from fiber volume fraction 40% to 60% and increases significantly from 60% to 70%. Further investigation is required to explain this completely, but it is believed that a sort of percolation threshold is reached, meaning that the matrix ligament distances between the fibers becomes small enough that the reduced interface toughness property dominates the fracture path.

Figure 4: Plot of modified tortuosity versus fiber volume fraction

The assertions made regarding the percolation threshold appear to be supported by the findings in Figure 5. Figure 5 highlights the relationship between the fraction of the crack which passes through the bulk matrix (not along the fiber/matrix interface) and the fiber volume fraction. The fraction of matrix cracking steadily decreases in the case of equal matrix and interface fracture toughness (red data in Figure 5). The interesting case is that of reduced interface fracture toughness (blue data in Figure 5). The data is once again approximately constant from 40% to 60% fiber volume fraction then significantly decreases from 60% to 70%. Thus, the sudden increase in modified tortuosity directly corresponds to the decrease in bulk matrix cracking.

Figure 5: Plot of fraction of fracture surface in the bulk matrix

4 CONCLUSIONS

A new measure of the tortuosity of a crack has been defined. This modified tortuosity has been shown to be sensitive to the fiber volume fraction and the bulk matrix and fiber/matrix interface fracture toughness properties. For material systems with weaker interfaces, the results may also indicate a percolation threshold related to the volume fraction (or consequently the bulk matrix ligament size) at which the crack strongly prefers interfacial failure to bulk matrix fracture. Future efforts will investigate the stability of these parameters to microstructures having more than ten fibers and with varying weakness of the interface fracture toughness.

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